

Observation of zero-energy edge states in rare-earth atomic chains on superconducting Nb(110) surface

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MZMs in 1D magnetic chains on SC

$$M(H_0) = (-1)^{v(\pi) - v(0)}$$

Bogoliubov quasiparticle bands

Kitaev A Yu 2001 Phys. Usp. 44 131
 PHYSICAL REVIEW B 90, 235433 (2014)
 B. W. Heinrich, *Progress in Surface Science*, vol. 93, no. 1
 F. V. Oppen, Oxford University Press Oxford, 2017, pp. 387–450.
 L. Schneider *et al*, *Nat. Phys.*, vol. 17, no. 8, pp. 943–948, Aug. 2021.
 L. Schneider *et al.*, *Nat. Nanotechnol.*, vol. 17, no. 4, pp. 384–389, Apr. 2022.

$$\xi_{\text{coupling}} \propto 1/\Delta_{\text{effective}}$$

Calculated energy spectra of 96 magnetic moments for 3d-metal YSR chains (blue lines).

D. Crawford, arXiv:2109.06894 [cond-mat.supr-con]
 Phys.Rev.B 90, 235433 (2014)
 Phys. Rev. B 88, 020407(R)
 PRL 111,147202 (2013)

Gd on Nb(110): Monomer & Dimers

$U_{\text{set}} = -7 \text{ mV}$
 $I_{\text{set}} = 0.4 \text{ nA}$
 $T = 1.4 \text{ K}$

Orbital decomposition and interaction of YSR states.
a Orbital-resolved superconducting DOS of short Gd dimer. The x and z directions are defined as the connecting vector of the Gd atoms and the Nb surface normal, respectively. The grey area marks the edges of the Nb(110) host's superconducting gap identified from the main coherence peak of Nb.
b Changes in the position of the YSR states for single atom and the different Gd dimers. **c** Sketch (top view) of the orbital hybridization in the short Gd dimer with the Nb substrate.

21Gd chain

Tb chains

- The discrepancy by comparing 21Nb-[110] lattice distance to the 21Gd-chain length
- By mapping the Gd atomic arrangement, a zig-zagged chain alignment is expected
- CO-functionalized tip has revealed zig-zagged chain arrangement on Tb chains
- The similar zig-zagged chain arrangement is on the [001]-oriented chains

Gd chains on Nb(110)

Tb chains on Nb(110)

$U_{\text{set}} = -7 \text{ mV}$
 $I_{\text{set}} = 0.4 \text{ nA}$
 $T = 1.4 \text{ K}$

(a,c,e): Constant-current STM image of a $[1\bar{1}0]$ chain of 9 Gd and two $[001]$ chains of 4 Gd and 5 Gd, and the corresponding dI/dU maps (b,d,f) in an external magnetic field $B_z = +0.5$ T. The two $[001]$ -oriented chains in dI/dU maps are marked by the black-dashed circles. The white arrow and white-dashed circles mark the 'double-tip' influence, respectively in topographic images and dI/dU maps. dI/dU is measured in arbitrary units (a.u.). Scale bar, 1 nm. Stabilization parameters: $U = -10$ mV, $I = 1$ nA, and $V_{\text{mod}} = 3$ mV.

- REMs chains relaxed zigzag on Nb(110) along [001]&[1-10]
- Total magnetic moments influence the system both directly and indirectly
- Heavy REM chains (Gd & Tb) exhibit Yu-Shiba-Rusinov (YSR) states, whereas light REM chains (Ce & La) do not
- Zero modes emerge exclusively on [001]-oriented Gd & Tb chains
- Evidence of a topologically non-trivial nature includes: Zero bias anomalies, YSR bands, mid-gap and magnetic state transition (FM \rightarrow spin-spiral)

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